

Apêndice A - Artigos selecionados na RSL

ID	Título	Autor(es)	Fonte	Ano
E002	"Now, I Have a Body": Uses and Social Norms for Mobile Remote Presence in the Workplace	Lee, Min Kyung; Takayama, Leila	Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2011
E005	A Case Study of Customer Communication in Globally Distributed Software Product Development	Korkala, Mikko; Pikkarainen, Minna; Conboy, Kieran	International Conference on Product Focused Software	2010
E007	A Comparative Empirical Study of Communication in Distributed and Collocated Development Teams	Al-Ani, Ban; Edwards, H. Keith	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008
E010	A Controlled Experiment on the Effects of Synchronicity in Remote Inspection Meetings	Calefato, Fabio; Lanubile, Filippo; Mallardo, Teresa	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	2007
E013	A framework to improve communication during the requirements elicitation process in GSD projects	Aranda, Gabriela N.; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Piattini, Mario	Requirements Engineering	2010

E036	Agile vs. Structured Distributed Software Development: A Case Study	Estler, H.-Christian; Nordio, Martin; Furia, Carlo a.; Meyer, Bertrand; Schneider, Johannes	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2012
E037	Aligning Software Maintenance to the Offshore Reality	Seybold, Christian; Keller, Rudolf K.	Conference on Software Maintenance and Reengineering	2008
E041	An Empirical Study of Global Software Development: Distance and Speed	Herbsleb, James D; Mockus, Audris; Finholt, Thomas A; Grinter, Rebecca E	International Conference on Software Engineering	2001
E043	An empirical study of requirements engineering in distributed software projects: is distance negotiation more effective?	Damian, Daniela	Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference	2001
E045	An Exploratory Study on Open Conversation Spaces In Software Engineering	Dullemond, Kevin; Gameren, Ben van; Solingen, Rini van	International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing	2011

E047	An Industrial Experience on the Application of Distributed Testing in an Agile Software Development Environment	Collins, Eliane; Macedo, Gisele; Maia, Nayane; Dias-Neto, Arilo	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2012
E061	Architectures, Coordination , and Distance : Conway's Law and Beyond	Herbsleb, James D; Grinter, Rebecca E	IEEE Software	1999
E063	Assessing the Impact of Real-Time Machine Translation on Requirements Meetings: A Replicated Experiment	Calefato, Fabio; Lanubile, Filippo; Conte, Tayana; Prikladnicki, Rafael	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	2012
E066	Automatic Status Updates in Distributed Software Development	King, Abayomi; Lyons, Kelly	International Workshop on Web 2.0 for Software Engineering	2011
E067	Awareness in the Wild: Why Communication Breakdowns Occur	Damian, Daniela; Izquierdo, Luis; Singer, Janice; Kwan, Irwin	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E070	Can distributed software development be agile?	Ramesh, Balasubramaniam; Cao, Lan; Mohan, Kannan; Xu, Peng	Communications Of The ACM	2006
E076	CodeSaw: A Social Visualization of Distributed Software Development	Gilbert, Eric; Karahalios, Karrie	International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction	2007

E080	Collaboration Patterns and the Impact of Distance on Awareness in Requirements-Centred Social Networks	Damian, Daniela; Marczak, Sabrina; Kwan, Irwin	International Conference on Requirements Engineering	2007
E082	Collaborative Embedded Systems Development: Survey of State of the Practice	Hyysalo, Jarkko; Parviainen, Päivi; Tihinen, Maarit	International Symposium and Workshop on Engineering of Computer Based Systems	2007
E086	Communication and Quality in Distributed Agile Development: An Empirical Case Study	Green, R; Mazzuchi, T; Sarkani, S	International Journal of Information and Communication Engineering	2010
E088	Communication in Distributed Agile Development: A Case Study	Korkala, Mikko; Abrahamsson, Pekka	Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications	2007
E089	Communication Metaphors-in-Use: Technical Communication and Offshore Systems Development	Wareha, Jonathan; Mahnke, Volker; Peters, Sanjay; Bjorn-Andersen, Niels	Transactions on Professional Communication	2007
E090	Communication Networks in Geographically Distributed Software Development	Cataldo, Marcelo; Herbsleb, James D	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2008

E092	Communication, coordination and control in distributed development: an OSS case study	Persson, Anna; Lings, Brian; Lundell, Björn; Mattsson, Anders; Ärlig, Ulf	International Conference on Open Source Systems	2005
E093	Communication, Knowledge and Co-ordination Management in Globally Distributed Software Development: Informed by a scientific Software Engineering Case Study	Taweel, Adel; Delaney, Brendan; Arvanitis, Theodoros N.; Zhao, Lei	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E094	Communications in Global Software Development: An Empirical Study Using GTK + OSS Repository	Yu, Liguu; Ramaswamy, Srin; Mishra, Alok; Mishra, Deepti	On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems Workshops	2011
E098	Computer-mediated communication to support distributed requirements elicitation and negotiations tasks	Calefato, Fabio; Damian, Daniela; Lanubile, Filippo	International Journal Empirical Software Engineering	2011
E104	Coordination Practices in Distributed Software Development of Small Enterprises	Boden, Alexander; Nett, Bernhard; Wulf, Volker	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E105	Coping with cultural and maturity inequality in offshore outsourcing: is minimizing interaction the solution ?	Hertzum, Morten; Pries-Heje, Jan	European Conference on Information Systems	

E106	Coping with Distance: An Empirical Study of Communication on the Jazz Platform	Sindhgatta, Renuka; Sengupta, Bikram; Datta, Subhajit	International Conference Companion on Object Oriented Programming Systems Languages and Applications	2011
E108	Critical issues of offshore software development project failures	Philip, T; Schwabe, G; Ewusi-Mensah, K	International Conference on Information Systems	2009
E110	Cultural and linguistic problems in GSD: a simulator to train engineers in these issues	Monasor, Miguel J; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Piattini, Mario	Journal of Software: Evolution And Process	2012
E112	CVS Integration with Notification and Chat: Lightweight Software Team Collaboration	Fitzpatrick, Geraldine; Marshall, Paul; Phillips, Anthony	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2006
E117	Design, Implementation, and Evaluation of a Virtual Meeting Tool-Based Innovation for UML Technology Training in Global Organizations	Koivulahti-Ojala, Mervi; Käkölä, Timo	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	2012
E120	Detecting and Classifying Patterns of Requirements Clarifications	Knauss, Eric; Damian, Daniela; Poocaamaño, Germán; Cleland-huang, Jane	International Conference on Requirements Engineering	2012

E127	Distributed Software Development Course: Students' and Teachers' Perspectives	Feljan, Juraj; Crnković, Ivica; Bosnić, Ivana; Orlić, Marin; Mario, Žagar	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2012
E137	Elicitation of Communication Inherent Risks in Distributed Software Development	Junior, Ivaldir H. De Farias; Azevedo, Ryan R. De; Moura, Hermano P. De; Silva, Dennis S. Martins Da	International Conference on Global Software Engineering Workshops	2012
E142	Essential communication practices for Extreme Programming in a global software development team	Layman, Lucas; Williams, Laurie; Damian, Daniela; Bures, Hynek	Information and Software Technology	2006
E146	Evolving an Infrastructure for Student Global Software Development Projects : Lessons for Industry	Gotel, Olly; Kulkarni, Vidya; Phal, Des; Say, Moniphall; Scharff, Christelle; Sunetnanta, Thanwadee	India Software Engineering Conference	2009
E147	Experiences of Instant Messaging in Global Software Development Projects: A Multiple Case Study	Niinimäki, Tuomas; Lassenius, Casper	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008

E151	Exploring the communication breakdown in global virtual teams	Daim, Tugrul U.; Ha, Anita; Reutiman, Shawn; Hughes, Brennan; Pathak, Ujjal; Bynum, Wayne; Bhatla, Ashok	International Journal of Project Management	2012
E152	Exploring the Media Mix during IT-Offshore Project	Wende, Erik; Schwabe, Gerhard; Philip, Tom	International Workshop on Global Sourcing of Information Technology and Business Processes	2010
E153	Exploring the Role of Instant Messaging in a Global Software Development Project	Dittrich, Yvonne; Giuffrida, Rosalba	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2011
E155	Extending Sociotechnical Congruence with Awareness Relationships	Kwan, Irwin; Damian, Daniela	International Workshop on Social Software Engineering	2011
E156	Extreme programming in global software development	Xiaohu, Yang; Bin, Xu; Zhijun, He	Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering	2004
E158	Factors Affecting Audio and Text-Based Communication Media Choice in Global Software Development Projects	Niinimaki, Tuomas; Piri, Arttu; Lassenius, Casper	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009

E160	Five Years of Lessons Learned from the Software Engineering Course: Adapting Best Practices for Distributed Software Development	Neto, Crescencio Rodrigues Lima; Almeida, Eduardo Santana de	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2012
E165	From RUP to Scrum in Global Software Development: A Case Study	Noordeloos, Ramon; Manteli, Christina; Vliet, Hans Van	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2012
E166	Fully Distributed Scrum: Linear Scalability of Production between San Francisco and India	Sutherland, Jeff; Schoonheim, Guido; Kumar, N.; Pandey, V.; Vishal, S.	Agile Conference	2009
E171	Global Software Development and Delay: Does Distance Still Matter?	Nguyen, Thanh; Wolf, Timo; Damian, Daniela	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008
E172	Global Software Development at Siemens: Experience from Nine Projects	Herbsleb, James D; Paulish, Daniel J; Bass, Matthew	International Conference on Software Engineering	2005
E173	Global software development projects in one of the biggest companies in Latvia: is geographical distribution a problem?	Šmite, Darja	Software Process: Improvement and Practice	2006
E175	Global Software Development: Who Does It?	Begel, Andrew; Nagappan, Nachiappan	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008

E177	Global Software Servicing: Observational Experiences at Microsoft	Bugde, Shilpa; Nagappan, Nachiappan; Rajamani, Sriram; Ramalingam, G.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008
E178	Global Virtual Teams: How to manage them	Johnston, K A; Rosin, K	International Conference on Computer and Management	2011
E181	Group Awareness in Distributed Software Development	Gutwin, Carl; Penner, Reagan; Schneider, Kevin	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2004
E188	How to Choose Groupware Tools Considering Stakeholders' Preferences During Requirements Elicitation?	Aranda, Gabriela N; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Cechich, Alejandra; Piatini, Mario	International Workshop on Groupware: Design, Implementation, and Use	2007
E192	IBM Industry Practice: Challenges in Offshore	Musio, Ilario	Software Engineering Approaches For Offshore and Outsourced Development	2009
E194	Impact of Changing Communication Media on Conflict Resolution in Distributed Software Development Projects	Khan, Huma Hayat; Malik, Nauman	Malaysian Conference in Software Engineering	2011

E197	Information Flow within a Dispersed Agile Team: A Distributed Cognition Perspective	Sharp, Helen; Giuffrida, Rosalba; Melnik, Grigori	International Conference on Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming	2012
E201	Intelligent Analysis of User Interactions in a Collaborative Software Engineering Context	Corbellini, Alejandro; Schiaffino, Silvia; Godoy, Daniela	Conferences on Advances in New Technologies, Interactive Interfaces and Communicability	2011
E203	Interaction Patterns among Global Software Development Learning Teams	Serce, Fatma Cemile; Swigger, Kathleen; Alpaslan, Ferda Nur; Brazile, Robert; Dafoulas, George; Lopez, Victor	International Symposium on Collaborative Technologies and Systems	2009
E208	Investigating an 'Agile-Rigid' Approach in Globally Distributed Requirements Analysis	Yadav, Vanita; Adya, Monica; Nath, Dhruv; Sridhar, V	Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems	2007
E212	Knowledge Management: A Solution to Requirements Understanding in Global Software Engineering	Khan, Hashim; Ahmad, Arshad; Alnuem, Mohammed A	Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology	2012

E216	Leadership Roles and Communication Issues in Partially Distributed Emergency Response Software Development Teams: A Pilot Study	Plotnick, Linda; Ocker, Rosalie; Hiltz, Starr Roxanne; Rosson, Mary Beth	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	2008
E218	Lessons Learned from an eXtremely Distributed Project	Hogan, Ben	Agile Conference	2006
E219	Leveraging expertise in global software teams: Going outside boundaries	Ehrlich, Kate; Chang, Klarissa	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2006
E224	Managing Communication among Geographically Distributed Teams: A Brazilian Case	Almeida, Ana Carina M; Junior, Ivaldir H De Farias; Carneiro, Pedro Jorge De S	Software Engineering Approaches For Offshore and Outsourced Development	2009
E226	Managing coordination and cooperation in distributed software processes: the GENESIS environment	Aversano, Lerina; De Lucia, Andrea; Gaeta, Matteo; Ritrovato, Pierluigi; Stefanucci, Silvio; Luisa Villani, Maria	Software Process: Improvement and Practice	2004

E227	Managing distributed software development in the Virtual Astronomical Observatory	Evans, Janet D.; Plante, Raymond L.; Boneventura, Nina; Busko, Ivo; Cresitello-Dittmar, Mark; D'Abrusco, Raffaele; Doe, Stephen; Ebert, Rick; Laurino, Omar; Pevunova, Olga; Refsdal, Brian; Thomas, Brian	SPIE Conference	2012
E230	Managing knowledge on communication and information flow in global software projects	Stapel, Kai; Schneider, Kurt	Expert Systems	2012
E235	Mastering Dual-Shore Development – The Tools and Materials Approach Adapted to Agile Offshoring	Kornstädt, Andreas; Sauer, Joachim	Software Engineering Approaches For Offshore and Outsourced Development	2007
E237	Media Choices and Trust in Partially Distributed Global Teams	Plotnick, Linda; Hiltz, Starr Roxanne; Ocker, Rosalie J	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	2010
E238	Media Choices over Time in Partially Distributed Teams	Plotnick, Linda; Hiltz, Starr Roxanne; Ocker, Rosalie J.	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	2012

E248	Mum Effect as an Offshore Outsourcing Risk: A Study of Differences in Perceptions	Sajeev, A.S.M.; Ramingwong, S.	The Computer Journal	2009
E252	Obtaining Requirements for Designing a Tool to Support Distributed Development	Hernández, José Luis; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Caballero, Ismael; Aranda, Gabriela	Journal of Universal Computer Science	2012
E254	Offshore middlemen: transnational intermediation in technology sourcing	Mahnke, Volker; Wareham, Jonathan; Bjorn-Andersen, Niels	Journal of Information Technology	2008
E261	Offshoring Attitudes, Relational Behaviours, And Departmental Culture	Não informado	European Conference on Information Systems	-
E262	On Coordination Mechanisms in Global Software Development	Cataldo, Marcelo; Bass, Matthew; Herbsleb, James D; Bass, Len	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E263	On Educating Globally Distributed Software Development - a Case Study Distances in GSD	Mäkiö, Juho; Betz, Stefanie	International Symposium on Computer and Information Sciences	2009
E264	On the Need for Mixed Media in Distributed Requirements Negotiations	Damian, Daniela; Lanubile, Filippo; Mallardo, Teresa	Transactions on Software Engineering	2008

E265	On The Roles of APIs in the Coordination of Collaborative Software Development	Souza, Cleidson R. B.; Redmiles, David F.	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2009
E276	Out of Sight but Not Out of Mind? Informal Networks , Communication and Media Use in Global Software Teams	Chang, Klarissa T; Ehrlich, Kate	Conference of The Center for Advanced Studies on Collaborative Research	2007
E282	Performing a Project in a Distributed Software Development Course: Lessons Learned	Ciccozzi, Federico; Crnkovic, Ivica	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E294	Providing Training in GSD by Using a Virtual Environment	Monasor, Miguel J; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Piattini, Mario	International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement	2012
E296	Quality indicators on global software development projects: does getting to know you' really matter?	Gotel, Olly; Kulkarni, Vidya; Say, Moniphal; Scharff, Christelle; Sunetnanta, Thanwadee	Journal of Software: Evolution And Process	2012
E300	Recommending Experts Using Communication History	Moraes, Alan; Silva, Eduardo; Trindade, Clayton; Barbosa, Yuri	International Workshop on Recommendation Systems for Software Engineering	2010

E301	Reflecting the choice and usage of communication tools in global software development projects with media synchronicity theory	Niinimäki, Tuomas; Piri, Arttu; Lasse- nius, Casper; Paasivaara, Maria	Journal of Soft- ware: Evolution And Process	2012
E304	Removing Barriers to Trust in Distributed Teams: Understanding Cultural Differences and Strengthening Social Ties	Mikawa, Suzanne P; Cunnington, Sharon K; Gask- ins, Scott A	International Workshop on Intercultural Collaboration	2009
E310	Requirements Understanding: A Challenge in Global Software Development, Industrial Surveys in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	Alnuem, Mo- hammed Ab- dullah; Ahmad, Arshad; Khan, Hashim	Computer Soft- ware and Appli- cations Confer- ence	2012
E321	Selective availability: coordinating interaction initiation in distributed software development	Palacio, R.R.; Morán, A L.; González, .M.; izcaíno, a.	IET Software	2012
E323	Shared Waypoints and Social Tagging to Support Collaboration in Software Development	Storey, Margaret-anne; Cheng, Li-Te; Bull, Ian; Rigby, Peter	International Conference on Computer Supported Co- operative Work	2006
E329	Sociomaterial bricolage: The creation of location-spanning work practices by global software developers	Johri, Aditya	Information and Software Technology	2011

E331	Software Architecture as a Means of Communication in a Globally Distributed Software Development Context	Svensson, Richard Berntsson; Aurum, Aybüke; Paech, Barbara; Gorschek, Tony; Sharma, Devesh	International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement	2012
E333	Software Engineering Across Boundaries: Student Project in Distributed Collaboration	JOHANSSON, CONNY; DITTRICH, YVONNE; JUUSTILA, ANTTI	Transactions on Professional Communication	1999
E344	Successful Collaborative Software Projects for Medical Devices in an FDA Regulated Environment: Myth or Reality?	Sudershana, Subita; Villcaroque, Abel; Baldanza, Jonathan	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E347	Supporting Collaboration in the Geographically Distributed Work with Communication Tools in the Remote District SME's	Liukkunen, Kari; Lindberg, Kai; Hyysalo, Jarkko; Markkula, Jouni	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E357	Teaching Students Global Software Engineering Skills using Distributed Scrum	Paasivaara, Maria; Lassenius, Casper; Damian, Daniela; Petteri, R; Schr, Adrian	International Conference on Software Engineering	2013

E364	Temporal coordination through communication: using genres in a virtual start-up organization	Im, Hyun-Gyung; Yates, JoAnne; Orlikowski, Wanda	Information Technology & People	2005
E375	The Impact of Media Selection on Stakeholder Communication in Agile Global Software Development: A Preliminary Industrial Case Study	Junius, Biyagama Agra; Hall, Tracy; Fitzpatrick, Anthony	Conference on Computer Personnel Research	2011
E376	The impact of stakeholders' geographical distribution on managing requirements in a multi-site organization	Damian, Daniela E; Zowghi, Didar	International Conference on Requirements Engineering	2007
E387	Tool to facilitate appropriate interaction in global software development	Palacio, R.R.; Vizcaíno, A.; Morán, J.L.; González, M.	IET Software	2011
E399	Towards an ontology for global software development	Vizcaíno, A.; García, F.; Caballero, I.; Villar, J.C.; Piattini, M.	IET Software	2011
E404	Trusty: A Tool to Improve Communication and Collaboration in DSD	Aranda, Gabriela Noemi; Vizcaíno, Aurora; Hernández, José Luís; Palacio, Ramón R; Morán, Alberto L	International Conference on Collaboration and Technology	2011

E405	Two Worlds Apart: Bridging the Gap Between Physical and Virtual Media for Distributed Design Collaboration	Everitt, Katherine M; Klemmer, Scott R; Lee, Robert; Landay, James A	Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2003
E407	Understanding Lacking Trust in Global Software Teams: A Multi-case Study	Moe, Nils Brede; Šmite, Darja	International Conference on Product-Focused Software Process Improvement	2007
E408	Using Audio and Collaboration Technologies for Distributed Requirements Elicitation and Documentation	Menten, Achim; Scheibmayr, Sven; Klimpke, Lars	International Workshop on Managing Requirements Knowledge	2010
E409	Using Content and Text Classification Methods to Characterize Team Performance	Swigger, Kathleen; Brazile, Robert; Dafoulas, George; Serce, Fatma Cemile; Alpaslan, Ferda Nur; Lopez, Victor	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E410	Using Developer Activity Data to Enhance Awareness during Collaborative Software Development	Omoronyia, Inah; Ferguson, John; Roper, Marc; Wood, Murray	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2009

E413	Using Scrum in Distributed Agile Development: A Multiple Case Study	Paasivaara, Maria; Durasiewicz, Sandra; Lassenius, Casper	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E421	Virtual Open Conversation Spaces: Towards Improved Awareness in a GSE Setting	Dullemond, Kevin; van Gameren, Ben; van Solingen, Rini	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E425	What Counts as Success? Punctuated Patterns of Use in a Persistent Chat Environment	Halverson, Christine A; Erickson, Thomas; Sussman, Jeremy	International Conference on Supporting Group Work	2003
E427	What Is Chat Doing in the Workplace?	Handel, Mark; Arbor, Ann; Herbsleb, James	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2002
E429	When No One's Home : Being a Remote Writer on Distributed Teams	Larbi, Nancy E; Springfield, Susan	International Professional Communication Conference	2003
E434	Work Item Tagging: Communicating Concerns in Collaborative Software Development	Treude, Christoph; Storey, Margaret-Anne	Transactions on Software Engineering	2012
E457	A Practical Management and Engineering Approach to Offshore Collaboration	Cusick, James; Prasad, Alpana	IEEE Software	2006

E458	A rule-based model for customized risk identification and evaluation of task assignment alternatives in distributed software development projects	Lamersdorf, Ansgar; Münch, Jürgen; Torre, Alicia Fernández- del Viso; Sánchez, Carlos Rebate; Heinz, Markus; Rombach, Dieter	Journal of Software: Evolution And Process	2012
E462	A Study of Collaboration in Software Design	Graham, James Wu T C N; Smith, Paul W	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering	2003
E469	Agile Practices Reduce Distance in Global Software Development	Holmström, Helena; Fitzgerald, Brian; Ågerfalk, Pär J.; Conchúir, Eoin Ó.	Information Systems Management	2006
E477	An empirical study of groupware support for distributed software architecture evaluation process	Babar, Muhammad Ali; Kitchenham, Barbara; Zhu, Liming; Gorton, Ian; Jeffery, Ross	Journal of Systems and Software	2006
E488	Assessing communication media richness in requirements negotiation	Erra, U.; Scanniello, G.	IET Software	2010

E493	Avoiding Scylla and Charybdis in Distributed Software Development Course	Bosnić, Ivana; Čavrak, Igor; Orlić, Marin; Žagar, Mario; Crnković, Ivica	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2011
E495	Back to Basics: The Role of Agile Principles in Success with an Distributed Scrum Team	Berczuk, Steve	Agile Conference	2007
E497	Bringing Global Sourcing into the Classroom: Experiential Learning via Software Development Project	Adya, Monica; Nath, Dhruv; Sridhar, Varadharajan; Malik, Amit	Conference on Computer personnel research	2007
E502	Can Real-Time Machine Translation Overcome Language Barriers in Distributed Requirements Engineering?	Calefato, Fabio; Lanubile, Filippo; Minervini, Pasquale	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E504	Collaboration in Global Software Projects at Siemens: An Experience Report	Bass, Matthew; Herbsleb, James D; Lescher, Christian	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E530	Developing Trust In Virtual Software Development Teams	Casey, Valentine	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	2010

E533	Differentiating Local and Global Systems Requirements Gathering Processes in IS Software Development Projects	Hanisch, Jo; Corbitt, Brian; Thanasankit, Theerasak	Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems	2005
E539	Distributed Versus Face-to-Face Meetings for Architecture Evaluation: A Controlled Experiment	Babar, Muhammad Ali; Kitchenham, Barbara; Jeffery, Ross	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering	2006
E543	Does Distributed Development Affect Software Quality? An Empirical Case Study of Windows Vista	Bird, Christian; Nagappan, Nachiappan; Devanbu, Premkumar; Gall, Harald; Murphy, Brendan	International Conference on Software Engineering	2009
E544	Effects of Four Distances on Communication Processes in Global Software Projects	Jaanu, Tuomas; Paasivaara, Maria; Lassenius, Casper	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	2012
E557	Experience and Recommendations for Distributed Software Development	Carlson, Patrick; Xiao, Nan	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2012

E558	Experiences in Global Software Development - A Framework-Based Analysis of Distributed Product Development Projects	Lane, Michael T.; Ågerfalk, Pär J.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E560	Experiments in Distributed Side-By-Side Software Development	Dewan, Prasan; Agrawal, Puneet; Hegde, Rajesh	International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing	2009
E568	Global Software Development Challenges: A Case Study on Temporal, Geographical and Socio-Cultural Distance	Holmstrom, Helena; Conchúir, Eoin Ó; Ågerfalk, Pär J; Fitzgerald, Brian	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2006
E569	Global Software Development: Are Architectural Rules the Answer?	Clerc, Viktor; Lago, Patricia; Vliet, Hans Van	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E572	Globally Distributed System Developers: Their Trust Expectations and Processes	Al-Ani, Ban; Bietz, Matthew J.; Wang, Yi; Trainer, Erik; Koehne, Benjamin; Marczak, Sabrina; Redmiles, David; Prikladnicki, Rafael	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2013

E581	Impact of Discrepancies in Effective Written Communication on Organizational Quality of Geographically Dispersed Software Organizations in Software Industry of Pakistan	Akram, Adnan; Ahsan, Dr. Ali	International Symposium on Management, Engineering and Informatics	2009
E589	Instructional Design and Assessment Strategies for Teaching Global Software Development: A Framework	Damian, Daniela; Hadwin, Allyson; Al-ani, Ban	International Conference on Software Engineering	2006
E591	Integration by communication: knowledge exchange in global outsourcing of product software development	Kristjánsson, Baldur; Helms, Remko; Brinkkemper, Sjaak	Expert Systems	2012
E594	Investigating the Role of organizational Structure in Developing Shared understanding of Requirements within GSD	Humayun, Mamoon; Gang, Cui	International Multitopic Conference	2012
E602	Knowledge Transfer in IT Offshore Outsourcing Projects: An Analysis of the Current State and Best Practices	Betz, Stefanie; Oberweis, Andreas; Stephan, Rolf	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010

E605	Management at the Outsourcing Destination - Global Software Development in India	Deshpande, Sadhana; Richardson, Ita	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E614	Mutual Dependency of Distribution , Benefits and Causes: An Empirical Study	Gumm, Dorina-c	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E615	Near-Synchronicity and Distance: Instant Messaging as a Medium for Global Software Engineering	Jaanu, Tuomas; Paasivaara, Maria; Lassenius, Casper	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2012
E616	Of Deadlocks and Peopleware - Collaborative Work Practices in Global Software Development	Avram, Gabriela	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E639	Student Motivation in Distributed Software Development Projects	Bosnić, Ivana; Čavrak, Igor; Orlić, Marin; Žagar, Mario	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2010
E641	Supporting Creative Collaboration in Globally Distributed Companies	Gumienny, Raja; Gericke, Lutz; Wenzel, Matthias; Meinel, Christoph	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2013
E643	Surviving the paradoxes of virtual teamwork	Dubé, Line; Robey, Daniel	Information Systems Journal	2008

E646	Teaching a Global Project Course: Experiences and Lessons Learned	Gloor, Peter; Paasivaara, Maria; Lassenius, Casper; Schoder, Detlef; Fischbach, Kai; Miller, Christine	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2011
E655	The Usefulness of Architectural Knowledge Management Practices in GSD	Clerc, Viktor; Lago, Patricia; Vliet, Hans Van	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E664	Uncovering the Reality Within Virtual Software Teams	Casey, Valentine; Richardson, Ita	International Workshop on Global Software Development for the Practitioner	2006
E666	Using a Real-Time Conferencing Tool in Distributed Collaboration: An Experience Report from Siemens IT Solutions and Services	Damian, Daniela; Marczak, Sabrina; Dascalu, Madalina; Heiss, Michael; Liche, Adrian	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2009
E672	Virtual team collaboration: building shared meaning, resolving breakdowns and creating translucence	Bjørn, Pernille; Ngwenyama, Ojelanki	Information Systems Journal	2009
E690	A risk profile of offshore-outsourced development projects	Iacovou, Charalambos L.; Nakatsu, Robbie	Communications Of The ACM	2008

E695	A Taxonomy and Visual Notation for Modeling Globally Distributed Requirements Engineering Projects	Laurent, Paula; Mäder, Patrick; Cleland-Huang, Jane; Steele, Adam	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E703	Advanced Hands-on Training for Distributed and Outsourced Software Engineering	Nordio, Martin; Mitin, Roman; Meyer, Bertrand	International Conference on Software Engineering	2010
E708	Ambidextrous coping strategies in globally distributed software development projects	Lee, Gwanhoo; Delone, William; Espinosa, J Alberto	Communications Of The ACM	2006
E714	An Evolving Collaborative Model of Working in Students' Global Software Development Projects	Scharff, Christelle	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2011
E729	Be successful, take a hostage or outsourcing the outsourcing Manager	Pichler, Horst	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007
E736	Collaboration in Software Development Lesson Learned from Two Large Multinational Organizations	Mettovaara, Vesa; Siponen, Mikko T.; Lehto, Jari A.	Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems	2006
E752	Cultural Perceptions og Tassk-Technology Fit	Massey, Anne P; Montoya-Weiss, Mitzi; Hung, Caisy; Ramesh, V	Communications Of The ACM	2001

E763	Distributed Development – an Education Perspective on the Global Studio Project	Richardson, Ita; Milewski, Allen E; Keil, Patrick; Mullick, Neel.	International Conference on Software Engineering	2006
E773	Empirical Study of Tool Support in Highly Distributed Research Projects	Prause, Christian R.; Reiners, Rene; Dencheva, Silviya	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2010
E774	Enabling Collaboration in Distributed Requirements Management	Sengupta, Bikram; Sinha, Vibha; Chandra, Satish	IEEE Software	2006
E788	Global Cooperative Design in Legacy System Reengineering Project	Xu, Bin; Yang, Xiaohu; He, Zhi-jun; Ma, Albert	Electronic Markets	2003
E795	Having a Foot on Each Shore - Bridging Global Software Development in the Case of SMEs	Richardson, Ita; Avram, Gabriela; Deshpande, Sadhana; Casey, Valentine	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008
E799	How Do Distribution and Time Zones Affect Software Development A Case Study on Communication	Nordio, Martin; Estler, H. Christian; Meyer, Bertrand; Tschannen, Julian; Ghezzi, Carlo; Nitto, Elisabetta Di	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2011
E806	Impression Formation in Online Peer Production Activity Traces and Personal Profiles in GitHub	Marlow, Jennifer; Dabbish, Laura; Herbsleb, Jim	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2013

E814	Inter-team Coordination in Large-Scale Globally Distributed Scrum Do Scrum-of-Scrums Really Work	Paasivaara, Maria; Lassenius, Casper; Heikkilä, Ville T.	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	2012
E825	Knowledge-related challenges and solutions in GSD	Parviainen, Päivi; Tihinen, Maarit	Expert Systems	2011
E827	Leveraging Resources in Global Software Development	Battin, Robert D.; Crocker, Ron; Kreidler, Joe; Subramanian, K.	IEEE Software	2001
E837	Managing the Iterative Requirements Process in a Multi-national Project Using an Issue Tracker	Prause, Christian R.; Scholten, Marius; Zimmermann, Andreas; Reiners, René; Eisenhauer, Markus	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2008
E845	Microblogging's Impact on Collaboration Awareness : a field study of microblogging within and between project teams	Zhao, Dejin; Rosson, Mary Beth; Matthews, Tara; Moran, Thomas	International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems	2011

E846	Mining Task-Based Social Networks to Explore Collaboration in Software Teams	Wolf, Timo; Schröter, Adrian; Damian, Daniela; Panjer, Lucas D; Nguyen, Thanh H.D.	IEEE Software	2009
E880	Siemens Global Studio Project Experiences Adopting an Integrated GSD Infrastructure	Mullick, Neel; Bass, Matthew; El Houda, Z; Paulish, Daniel J; Cataldo, M; Herbsleb, J D; Bass, L	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2006
E885	Supporting Acceptance Testing in Distributed Software Projects with Integrated Feedback Systems: Experiences and Requirements	Liskin, Olga; Herrmann, Christoph; Knauss, Eric; Kurpick, Thomas; Rumpe, Bernhard; Schneider, Kurt	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2012
E891	TAPER A generic framework for establishing an offshore development center	Höfner, Gerd; Mani, V S	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2007

E893	Teaching Software Engineering using Globally Distributed Projects: The DOSE Course	Nordio, Martin; Ghezzi, Carlo; Meyer, Bertrand; Nitto, Elisabetta Di; Tamburrelli, Giordano; Tschannen, Julian; Aguirre, Nazareno; Kulkarni, Vidya	Workshop on Collaborative Teaching of Globally Distributed Software Development	2011
E898	The Impact of Multi-site Software Governance on Knowledge Management	Manteli, Christina; Hooff, Bart Van Den; Tang, Antony; Vliet, Hans Van	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2011
E902	The Software Engineering Impacts of Cultural Factors on Multi-cultural Software Development Teams	Borchers, Greg	International Conference on Software Engineering	2003
E903	Tool Support for Distributed Software Engineering	Spanjers, Hans; Hurne, Maarten; Bendas, Dan; Graaf, Bas; Lormans, Marco; Solingen, Rini van	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2006
E908	Towards Agility In Design In Global Component - Based Development	KOTLARSKY, JULIA; Oshri, Ilan; Kumar, Kuldeep; Hillegersberg, Jos Van	Communications Of The ACM	2008

E912	Understanding the functions of teleconferences for coordinating global software development projects	Wiredu, Gamel O.	Information Systems Journal	2011
E924	Figure out how to code with the hands of others: recognizing cultural blind spots in global software development	Stina Matthiesen, Pernille Bjørne Lise Møller Petersen	Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2014
E925	In the Flow, Being Heard, and Having Opportunities: Sources of Power and Power Dynamics in Global Teams	Pamela Hinds, Daniela Retelny, Catherine Cramton	Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2015
E926	Mudslinging and Manners: Unpacking Conflict in Free and Open Source Software	Anna Filippova e Hichang Cho	Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work	2015
E927	Leadership styles and their effect on the structure of communication response patterns among global virtual teams	Ian Brooks; Kathy Swigger	International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems	2014
E928	A collaborative framework for supporting combined visualization of activities across time zones	Paolo Buono; Alfredo Cuzocrea	International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems	2015

E929	Effects of cohesion-based feedback on the collaborations in global software development teams	Alberto Castro-Hernández; Kathleen Swigger; Mirna P. Ponce-Flores	International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing	2015
E930	Sentiment Identification for Collaborative, Geographically Dispersed, Cross-Functional Software Development Teams	Amol Patwardhan	International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing	2017
E931	On the Role of Boundary Spanners as Team Coordination Mechanisms in Organizationally Distributed Projec	Anh Nguyen-Duc; Daniela S. Cruzes; Reidar Conrad	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2014
E932	Extending Survivability Models for Global Software Development with Media Synchronicity Theory	Alberto Avritzer; Sarah Beecham; Ricardo Britto; Josiane Kroll; Daniel Sadoc Menasche; John Noll; Maria Paasivaara...	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2015
E933	An Empirical Investigation on Effort Estimation in Agile Global Software Development	Ricardo Britto; Emilia Mendes; Jürgen Börstler.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2015

E934	Communication between Developers and Testers in Distributed Continuous Agile Testing	Daniela S. Cruzes; Nils B. Moe; Tore Dybå.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2016
E935	Understanding Architectural Knowledge Sharing in AGSD Teams: An Empirical Study	Gilberto Borreg,; Alberto L. Morán, Ramón Palacio e Oscar M. Rodríguez	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2016
E936	Does latitude hurt while longitude kills? geographical and temporal separation in a large scale software development project	Patrick Wagstrom, Subhajit Datta	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2014
E937	Teaching a global software development course: student experiences using onsite exercise simulation	Jouni Lappalainen, Nirnaya Tripathi e Jouni Similä	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2016
E938	Routine and Standardization in Global Software Development	Morten Esbensen e Pernille Bjørn	International Conference on Supporting Group Work	2016
E939	Why Closely Coupled Work Matters in Global Software Development	Rasmus Eskild Jensen	International Conference on Supporting Group Work	2014
E940	Disaggregating the Impacts of Virtuality on Team Identification	Lionel P. Robert, Sangseok You	International Conference on Supporting Group Work	2018

E941	An empirical simulation-based study of real-time speech translation for multilingual global project teams	Fabio Calefato, Filippo Lanubile, Rafael Prikladnicki	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	2014
E942	On the Identification of Factors that Promote High-Performance Projects in Distributed Development	Sabrina Marczak, Marcelo Perin, Rafael Prikladnicki, Christiano Ayub.	Workshop on Distributed Software Development, Software Ecosystems, and Systems-of-Systems	2014
E943	Data collection in global software engineering research: learning from past experience	Rafael Prikladnicki, Alexander Boden, Gabriela Avram, Cleidson R. B. de Souza E Volker Wulf	Empirical Software Engineering	2014
E944	How product owner teams scale agile methods to large distributed enterprises	Julian M. Bass	Empirical Software Engineering	2014
E945	Assessing the impact of real-time machine translation on multilingual meetings in global software projects	Fabio Calefato, Filippo Lanubile, Tayana Conte e Rafael Prikladnicki	Empirical Software Engineering	2015
E946	Cheap talk, cooperation, and trust in global software engineering	Yi Wang e David Redmiles	Empirical Software Engineering	2015

E947	How does developer interaction relate to software quality? an examination of product development data	Subhajit Datta	Empirical Software Engineering	2018
E948	Agile Collaboration for Distributed Teams [Software Technology]	Fabio Calefato e Christof Ebert	IEEE Software	2019
E949	Facilitating contagion trust through tools in Global Systems Engineering teams	Ban Al-Ani, Sabrina Marczak, David Redmiles e Rafael Prikladnicki	Information and Software Technology	2014
E950	A tool supporting root cause analysis for synchronous retrospectives in distributed software teams	Timo O. A Lehtinen, Risto Virtanen, Juha O. Viljanen, Mika V. Mäntylä, Casper Lassenius.	Information and Software Technology	2014
E951	Categorization of risk factors for distributed agile projects	Supriya V. Shrivastava e Urvashi Rathod	Information and Software Technology	2015
E952	A conceptual framework to study the role of communication through social software for coordination in globally-distributed software teams	Rosalba Giuffrida e Yvonne Dittrich	Information and Software Technology	2015
E953	Communication and personality profiles of global software developers	Sherlock A. Licorish, Stephen G. MacDonell	Information and Software Technology	2015

E954	A theory of distances in software engineering	Elizabeth Bjarnason, Kari Smolander, Emelie Engström, Per Runeson.	Information and Software Technology	2016
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E956	A risk management framework for distributed agile projects	Suprika Vasudeva Shrivastava e Urvashi Rathod	Information and Software Technology	2017
E957	ARSENAL-GSD: A framework for trust estimation in virtual teams based on sentiment analysis	Guilherme Augusto Maldonado da Cruza, Elisa Hatsue Moriya-Huzita, Valéria Delisandra Feltrim	Information and Software Technology	2018
E958	Age stereotypes in distributed software development: The impact of culture on age-related performance expectations	Uta Schloegel, Sebastian Stegmann, Rolf van Dick, Alexander Maedche	Information and Software Technology	2018
E959	Quality requirements challenges in the context of large-scale distributed agile: An empirical study	Wasim Alsaqaf, Maya Daneva e Roel Wieringa	Information and Software Technology	2019

E960	Skills and abilities for working in a global software development team: a competence model	Javier Saldaña-Ramos, Ana Sanz-Esteban, Javier García e Antonio Amescua	Journal of Software: Evolution and Process	2014
E961	How software development competences change in global settings—an explorative study	Philipp Holtkamp, Ivan Lau e Jan Martin Pawlowski	Journal of Software: Evolution and Process	2014
E962	A conceptual framework of challenges and solutions for managing global software maintenance	Bayarbuyan Ulziit, Zeeshan Akhtar Waraich , Cigdem Gencel e Kai Petersen	Journal of Software: Evolution and Process	2015
E963	Dynamics of task allocation in global software development	Salma Imtiaz AND Naveed Ikram	Journal of Software: Evolution and Process	2016
E964	Onboarding software developers and teams in three globally distributed legacy projects: A multi-case study	Ricardo Britto, Daniela S. Cruzes, Darja Smite e Aivars Sablis	Journal of Software: Evolution and Process	2017
E965	Waste identification as the means for improving communication in globally distributed agile software development	Mikko Korkala e Frank Maurer	Journal of Systems and Software	2014

E966	Bridging the gap between awareness and trust in globally distributed software teams	Erik H. Trainer and David F. Redmiles	Journal of Systems and Software	2018
E967	How Social and Communication Channels Shape and Challenge a Participatory Culture in Software Development	Margaret-Anne Storey, Alexey Zagalsky, Fernando Figueira Filho, Leif Singer e Daniel M. German	Transactions on Software Engineering (TSE)	2017
E968	Communication Network in an Agile Distributed Software Development Team	Paul T. Robinson	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2019
E969	Behavior-Driven Development as an Approach to Improve Software Quality and Communication Across Remote Business Stakeholders, Developers and QA: two Case Studies	André Scandaroli, Rodrigo Leite; Aléxis H. Kiosia; Sandro A. Coelho	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2019
E970	Slack Me If You Can! Using Enterprise Social Networking Tools in Virtual Agile Teams	Stray, Viktoria, Nils Brede Moe, and Mehdi Noroozi.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2019
E971	A case study on tool support for collaboration in agile development	Calefato, F., Giove, A., Lanubile, F., & Losavio, M.	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2020

E972	Understanding collaborative software development: an interview study	Constantino, K., Zhou, S., Souza, M., Figueiredo, E., & Kästner, C	International Conference on Global Software Engineering	2020
E973	"How Was Your Weekend?" Software Development Teams Working From Home During COVID-19	Miller, C., Rodeghero, P., Storey, M. A., Ford, D., & Zimmermann, T.	Conferência Internacional sobre Engenharia de Software (ICSE)	2021
E974	Quality requirements challenges in the context of large-scale distributed agile: An empirical study	Alsaqaf, Wasim, Maya Daneva, and Roel Wieringa.	Information and Software Technology	2019
E975	Overcoming cultural barriers to being agile in distributed teams	Šmite, Darja, Nils Brede Moe, and Javier Gonzalez-Huerta.	Information and Software Technology	2021
E976	Constructing continuity across the organisational culture boundary in a highly virtual work environment	Asatiani, A., Hämäläinen, J., Penttinen, E., & Rossi, M.	Information Systems Journal	2020
E977	The Influence of Themes of Interplay on Multi Stakeholders Engagement Amidst Adversities in Globally Distributed ICT Projects – A Case Study Approach	Mysore, K., Elmualim, A., & Kirytopoulos, K.	Journal of Global Information Technology Management	2019

E978	Group maturity, team efficiency, and team effectiveness in software development: A case study in a CMMI-DEV Level 5 organization	Ramírez-Mora, S. L., Oktaba, H., & Patlan Perez, J.	Journal of Software: Evolution and process	2019
E979	GLOB: A global project management readiness framework	Niazi, M., Mahmood, S., & Alshayeb, M.	Journal of Software: Evolution and process	2020
E980	Team-external coordination in large-scale software development projects	Sablis, A., Smite, D., & Moe, N.	Journal of Software: Evolution and process	2020
E981	Software architecture design in global software development: An empirical study	Sievi-Korte, O., Richardson, I., & Beecham, S.	Journal of Systems and Software	2019
E982	Leading successful government-academia collaborations using FLOSS and agile values	Wen, M., Siqueira, R., Lago, N., Camarinha, D., Terceiro, A., Kon, F., & Meirelles, P.	Journal of Systems and Software	2020
E983	Evaluating and strategizing the onboarding of software developers in large-scale globally distributed projects	Britto, R., Smite, D., Damm, L. O., & Börstler, J.	Journal of Systems and Software	2020
E984	Understanding coordination in global software engineering: A mixed-methods study on the use of meetings and Slack	Stray, V., & Moe, N. B.	Journal of Systems and Software	2020

E985	Do scaling agile frameworks address global software development risks? An empirical study	Beecham, S., Clear, T., Lal, R., & Noll, J.	Journal of Systems and Software	2021
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Table 19: Artigos selecionados na RSL